

D5.3

Pilot Demonstrators (M26)

WODR

D5.3

Pilot Demonstrators (M26)

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Abstract

Initial version of the demonstrators.

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Nature of the deliverable

DEM

Dissemination level

PU Public, fully open. e.g., website

✓

CL Classified information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

SEN Confidential to DATAMITE project and Commission Services

* Deliverable types:

R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).

DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIM	Agriculture Information Model
AIoD	Artificial Intelligence on Demand
API	Application Programming Interface
CD	Continuous Delivery
CI	Continuous Integration
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DIH	Digital Innovation Hubs
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable principles
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OLAP	Online Analytical Processing
OLTP	Online Transaction Processing
PaaS	Platform as a Service
RAM	Random-Access Memory
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
VM	Virtual Machine
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

DATAMITE is a project funded by the European Commission as part of the Horizon Europe program and coordinated by the ITI - Technological Institute of Informatics. DATAMITE empowers European companies by delivering a modular, open-source and multi-domain Framework to improve DATA Monetizing, Interoperability, Trading and Exchange, in the form of software modules, training, and business materials.

DATAMITE unleashes the monetization potential at two levels. At internal level, users will have tools to improve quality management of their data, the adherence to FAIR principles, and their ability to upskill on technical and business aspects thanks to the multiple open-source training materials the project will generate. Therefore, data will become trustworthy and more reliable also in other paradigms like AI.

At external level, keeping users in control of their data will provide new sources of revenue and interaction with other stakeholders. The architecture envisioned for DATAMITE enables DIHs sandboxing, becoming a potential facilitator in onboarding SMEs and low-tech SMEs into the data economy. Together, DATAMITE's solutions will function as a catalyst to boost data monetization in the European productive fabric.

1.1 Deliverable Purpose and Scope

Specifically, the Grant Agreement states the following regarding this Deliverable:

Initial version of the demonstrators.

Hence, the purpose of this document is to present the progress in integrating the key components of the DATAMITE framework and to verify the system's functionality within pilot deployments. The document aims to demonstrate how the DATAMITE solution performs in various operational environments, showcasing both the flexibility of its configuration and its ability to adapt to specific requirements – from deployments on cloud platforms to in-house solutions used for security and integration purposes.

The scope of the document includes a detailed description of the real-world demonstration strategy, including the continuous integration (CI/CD) procedures developed in Task 5.1. It also presents the preliminary results of technical, operational, and security efforts that form the foundation for demonstrating the system's functionality in the pilots developed under Task 5.2. D5.3 serves not only as a status report, but primarily, as a demonstrator and a reference for future

development activities, enabling further optimization and adaptation of the framework to meet the requirements of subsequent deployments.

1.2 Document Structure

This deliverable is broken down into the following sections:

- **Section 1 Introduction** provides the deliverable's general context, dependencies, and structure.
- **Section 2 Continuous Integration of the DATAMITE Components** presents the integration, including CI/CD tools, procedures and guidelines.
- **Section 3 Pilot Demonstrators** carries out on the pilot demonstrators developed within the DATAMITE project. It provides links to each pilot's demo materials. This section illustrates how the integrated system performs in real-world settings, showcasing its adaptability and effectiveness in meeting diverse operational requirements.
- **Appendix A** contains the Pilot 2 test scenario queries.
- **Appendix B** contains the Pilot 5 screenshots of DATAMITE platform deployment.

1.3 Document Dependencies

This document constitutes the first iteration of the deliverable, presenting the current status of the integration of DATAMITE components and the pilot demonstration. In particular, it includes information on progress in software development, system integration, and demonstration activities. The work is based on an initial analysis of the pilots in accordance with D1.1 Roadmap and Pilots' Definitions. The demonstrations are associated with the technical requirements derived from the assumptions underlying the pilot implementations, which have influenced the project's architecture and have been defined in D1.2 Requirements and Architecture. Additionally, data management plans for the pilots, as described in Deliverables D7.7 and D7.8 (Data Management Plan and Data Protection Plan), have also been taken into account. In the final phase of the project (M32), the initial version of the demonstrators will be updated to the final version - Deliverable 5.4.

2 Continuous Integration of the DATAMITE Components

The section provides a detailed overview of the continuous integration practices employed in the DATAMITE project (Task 5.1). It outlines the CI/CD tools, integration procedures, and guidelines used to ensure a smooth and efficient deployment process, as well as an overview of the framework releases that maintain system stability and quality.

2.1 CI/CD tools

This subsection outlines the essential tools required for CI/CD procedures. Specifically, the GitLab repository serves as the central repository for the framework, while the DockerHub account is used to manage Docker images.

GitLab Repository:

<https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/DATAMITE-project>

DockerHub:

<https://hub.docker.com/search?q=DATAMITE>

2.2 CI procedures and integration guidelines

This subsection describes the pipelines and the relevant stages for committing to the framework.

Pipelines:

https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/DATAMITE-project/docs/-/blob/main/ci_cd.md?ref_type=heads

2.3 Releases of the DATAMITE framework

This subsection discusses the releases of the DATAMITE framework. The current release focuses on a Docker Swarm implementation, while a Kubernetes deployment is planned for a future release. Additionally, the data-sharing logging tool and the AI on Demand Broker have been documented. As a next step, all framework components will be documented, and a central repository for documentation will be established by adding the URLs of all components to the GitLab Wiki page.

Release 1:

https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/DATAMITE-project/data-support-tools/data_ingestion_and_storage/infrastructure

Documentation:

DATAMITE's Logging tool:

<https://DATAMITE-logging-tool.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>

DATAMITE's brokering service for the AI on Demand Platform:

<https://aiod-broker.readthedocs.io/en/latest/introduction.html>

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3 Pilot Demonstrators

The DATAMITE project infrastructure and software were deployed using a strategic approach tailored to the specific requirements of each pilot. Different configurations were employed to ensure optimal performance and scalability in various environments – for instance, some pilots utilised dedicated virtual machines on cloud platforms such as Azure or Google Cloud, while others relied on in-house solutions to meet specific security or integration needs. This diversified deployment strategy not only supports the seamless integration of key modules but also enables the framework to adapt to various data exchange protocols and operational constraints.

A summary is in the table below:

Pilot no.	Pilot name	Infrastructure
Pilot 1	Corporate Multi-Domain Data Exchange with EDIH support	2 VMs (Ubuntu) Private CPD
Pilot 2	Corporate Multi-Site Data Exchange	2 VMs (Linux) in Azure
Pilot 3	Offering Data to Service Providers with DataSpaces	VM (Ubuntu) on Google Cloud Platform
Pilot 4	Leveraging Electricity Distribution Open Data	VM (Windows) and Storage Account in Azure
Pilot 5	Connecting eDWIN to Data Markets	IaaS (OpenStack – bare VMs, various architecture) / PaaS (OpenShift)
Pilot 6	Connecting MISTRAL to the EU AloD Platform	1 VM (Ubuntu) in-house cloud

Table 1. Pilots deployed infrastructure.

3.1 Pilot 1: Corporate Multi-Domain Data Exchange with EDIH support Demonstrator

3.1.1 Current status

GIDI is centred on the correct deployment of DATAMITE according to the standards and security requirements of the group, particularly in terms of architecture and best practices.

The DATAMITE testing framework has been successfully deployed without any issues. Apart from this, only a few configurations remain pending. This setup is related to the connection of DATAMITE to our testing architecture. After conversations with the development team, we think it will be better to have a direct connection to databases and repositories. Using API (REST) or any other intermediary technology is not recommended at this point.

Once these details are resolved, we will proceed to develop the testing experience, following the process whose diagrams are covered deeply in D5.1. The final behaviour and capabilities of DATAMITE modules could produce changes in the demonstration pipelines, which will be described in this document only if they occur.

For the second half of 2025, particularly during the second round of testing, we plan to incorporate changes suggested by technical partners, as well as improvements based on our own experience from the first round of testing.

3.1.2 Demonstrator

Below are a variety of videos presenting the implementation of Pilot 1. These videos focus on the advances in pilot 1 testing, which are adapted to the status of the DATAMITE infrastructure. These videos serve as demonstrators, detailing the platform's operation directly from a frontend approach. The provided materials focus on dataset uploading, simple glossary management, and access to description metrics. One relevant point in our pilot is the possibility of accessing datasets which have been published for different users (companies). This aspect will be tested when the DATAMITE development team deploys the authentication module.

[Pilot 1 Demonstrators](#)

At this link are nine videos presenting the pilot demonstrator.

3.2 Pilot 2: Corporate Multi-Site Data Exchange Demonstrator

3.2.1 Current status

Currently, OTE Group focuses on implementing a unified metadata model and a central repository to enable consistent data management across the organisation. Work is being done to deploy middleware that automates the integration of various repositories and a standardised query language (Appendix A: Pilot 2 test scenarios queries) to facilitate data access. Test scenarios for Online Analytical Processing (OLAP) and Online Transaction Processing (OLTP) are being introduced to identify and correct data inconsistencies in the systems.

OTE has deployed two publicly accessible servers designed as a cluster to utilise the Trino tool. Both servers include a user interface that allows for extracting the repository's key performance metrics. Additionally, the first version of a synthetic data generator has been developed, which can be used to evaluate the system's performance.

In terms of hardware specifications, the two servers operate within an in-house cloud orchestrator. One server runs Ubuntu 22.04, while the other one runs Debian 12. Both machines are equipped with the latest Java version (23.0.2, as required by Trino) and the latest Docker version, which is used for the DATAMITE infrastructure setup. Each server has 24GB of RAM and 8 CPU cores, with dynamic scaling enabled to adjust to workload requirements. Storage capacity is also dynamically adjusted as volume storage is utilised to meet varying demands.

3.2.2 Demonstrator

The deployment phase of DATAMITE has also been implemented on those servers. One of them, accessible at <http://147.102.74.122:3000/dashboard>, hosts the full framework of DATAMITE, integrating all the available modules. Furthermore, Appendix A: Pilot 2 test scenarios queries presents two related queries that can be executed within the lab environment to demonstrate the overall concept of the test scenarios that are being analysed in the corresponding Pilot 2 section of Deliverable D5.1.

Moreover, CERTH has deployed an additional server that hosts the user interface of the data product composition module, tailored to the pilot's architecture. This server provides enhanced functionality for data interaction and visualisation, complementing the existing infrastructure. It can be accessed at <https://DATAMITE.api.tools.iti.gr/#/data-sources>, providing a dedicated specialized environment for managing and exploring data sources efficiently.

3.3 Pilot 3: Offering Data to Service Providers with Data Spaces Demonstrator

3.3.1 Current status

Currently, HEDNO has implemented the first iteration of Pilot 3's demonstration, which involves data collection and preparation from its infrastructure, integration of its internal systems with the DATAMITE framework and composition of data products. A virtual machine running Ubuntu Server 24.04 was used to deploy the DATAMITE components. Close collaboration with the tools developers has led to a swift resolution of issues and an overall enhancement of the capabilities and functionalities of the software platform.

The second iteration, which will conclude the demonstration and validation plan, will focus on improving data quality, implementing access policies, and enabling data product sharing through an Energy Data Space. Challenges include improving data-sharing processes, ensuring interoperability, and maintaining compliance with data protection regulations.

3.3.2 Demonstrator

Demonstration videos were created for each iteration of the pilot's validation plan. Each video covers all the steps involved in a scenario from the demonstration.

The [video for Scenario 1](#) showcases the creation of datasets using files from several sources (in Pilot 3's case, the sources are Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI) smart meter measurements, Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) measurements and PowerFactory network files). First, the glossary and terms that accurately describe the data product are defined by filling all fields. Then, a dataset is created by associating it with a glossary and terms, selecting raw files for upload and finally setting access permissions. The video also demonstrates the creation of a dataset by connecting with an existing PostgreSQL database where data has been previously stored. Finally, the video concludes with an overview of the data catalogue after the creation of all datasets has been completed. The video also demonstrates the creation of a dataset by connecting with an existing PostgreSQL database where data has been previously stored. Finally, the video concludes with an overview of the data catalogue after the creation of all datasets has been completed.

In the [video for Scenario 2](#), we consider data product composition and anonymisation techniques to protect sensitive information. First, we create data products by leveraging the aggregation

capabilities of the *Data Product Composition* component. This process involves merging multiple datasets into a single file and bundling diverse datasets from different sources into a composite archive. Then, all steps of the data anonymisation procedure are showcased using the Swagger API, by loading a data product and selecting a column with private data to be hidden. Examples of applying several anonymisation techniques to obscure its contents are provided, and their outputs are verified by visually inspecting the API response and downloading and viewing the anonymised data locally. The video concludes by showing the creation and execution of a Trino query to retrieve information from a PostgreSQL database that contains smart meter measurements.

3.4 Pilot 4: Leveraging Electricity Distribution Open Data Demonstrator

3.4.1 Current status

Currently, E-REDES has implemented the first phase of Pilot 4, focusing on data collection, validation, and sharing of open datasets through internal systems and integration with the DATAMITE framework. Work is underway to define data quality rules and implement metadata extraction tools, which will be stored in the metadata repository. The next phase, scheduled for completion by September 2025, will involve testing and sharing data products within the CEEDS energy data space and ensuring interoperability with the E-REDES open data portal. Key challenges remain in automating data-sharing processes, ensuring compliance with IDS and GAIA-X requirements, and assessing the economic impact of investing in data space integration.

3.4.2 Demonstrator

For Pilot 4, there are two implementation demos. The first demo, which is related to the first scenario of the demonstration, shows the Azure Connector, which extracts the datasets metadata from the Azure Storage Account. The second demo, which is also related to the first scenario of the demonstration, exemplifies the deployment and testing of the DATAMITE framework prototype presented at the Aachen Codecamp. Both demos are a result of the first iteration phase.

Demo 1 - [Azure Connector](#)

This video showcases the Data Discovery Connectors establishing a connection to the pilot's storage in Azure. For this purpose, the component uses the Azure connector to retrieve the metadata information available in the Azure Data Lake Gen2.

For simplicity, consider that Azure Storage Account and Azure Data Lake Gen2 refer to the same storage in the pilot's infrastructure. Although there are some technical differences, they are beyond the scope of this context.

At the beginning of the video, the datasets available in the Azure Storage Account are shown. There are six datasets stored. The goal of the connector is to extract the metadata of these six datasets.

For the connector to function properly, the corresponding component needs to be running. Docker is used for that purpose. The next part of the video demonstrates how to run the docker container of the Data Discovery Connectors.

To confirm the component is running, an API call is performed in the application's Swagger interface. The request body is modified to include the credentials necessary to access the Azure Data Lake. In the response body, it is possible to see, for each of the six datasets, the name, the file type, the size, and the date of last modification. Another parameter to verify the API calls is the response code: if it is 200, then the request was successful; a different code indicates otherwise.

Given the pilot's implementation will use Databricks to connect the multiple components, it is paramount to test the same API calls within Databricks. A link to Databricks cannot be provided since it is for E-REDES access only. The Databricks infrastructure used can be observed in the videos. The next part of the video demonstrates this. In a notebook, the required PySpark libraries ([requests](#) and [json](#)) are imported to perform an API call. Then, the API's parameters - endpoint, header, and payload – need to be specified. With this information, the request can be placed. Lastly, the response needs to be processed to be readable. By checking the processed response, it is possible to confirm that it is identical to the response in the application's Swagger interface, which means the request was successful.

In summary, the component was running in a Docker container. Subsequently, API calls confirmed the component is working correctly. Lastly, the Databricks API call demonstrates the connection between the Docker container in the VM and the Databricks resource in Azure. Therefore, the pilot is now ready to establish a connection of the Data Discovery Connector with the other components to share the dataset's metadata.

Demo 2 – [Framework Prototype](#)

This video demonstrates the deployment of the DATAMITE framework prototype in E-REDES premises. The prototype is the first bundle version of the DATAMITE framework that was made

available by the technical partners to the pilots for deployment on the internal premises. It is composed of data quality and governance components. To achieve the implementation, it includes the necessary pipelines that establish connections to support the upload of new datasets.

The prototype was developed by the technical team, which presented it at the plenary meeting in November in Aachen. The prototype's code was made available so the pilots could implement the framework in their respective infrastructure. Thus, the video will show the prototype's implementation and a dataset upload through the frontend interface.

The video starts by cloning the code from the repository shared by the technical team. Once the code is in the virtual machine (VM) of the pilot's infrastructure, the setup of the necessary files for deployment begins. The file required to create is `cluster.json`, which must have the configuration details necessary for the Docker swarm. These details include external IP address, IP address of the manager Docker node, IP addresses of worker Docker nodes, and the filename storing the environment variables.

In the repository, there is a script to automatically create the Docker swarm configured by the details in the `cluster.json` file. For pilot 4, there will only be one worker node since the infrastructure only has one VM. Therefore, that one VM will be the Docker swarm manager assigned by the script.

With the Docker swarm configured, it is possible to deploy the prototype services. The prototype will be deployed once every service has at least 1/1 replica running.

When the framework is deployed, it is possible to access the framework using the external IP address, configured in the `cluster.json` file, on port 3000. This will lead to the DATAMITE frontend where the user can upload datasets and access the associated information.

The video will show an example of uploading a dataset stored in CSV format. Afterwards, the dataset will be available among the data artefacts, and the user can access the metrics of each one. At the time of the video, the User Defined Rules Generator (UDRG) was not included in the prototype, hence the absence of values in the KPIs table.

In conclusion, the video shows the cloning of the prototype's code, the configuration of the file to form the Docker swarm, deployment of the services, uploading a dataset, and checking associated data artefacts and KPIs. This demonstrates the pilot infrastructure's ability to support the deployment of the framework.

3.5 Pilot 5: Connecting eDWIN to Data Markets Demonstrator

3.5.1 Current status

Pilot 5 integrates the [eDWIN](#) and [Agrego](#) platforms to enable seamless data exchange via the DATAMITE platform. eDWIN serves as the core system, providing APIs for data access and supporting various user applications. It employs Apache Kafka for data processing and storage, and its Identity and Access Management (IAM) system ensures secure authentication through OpenID Connect (OIDC) and OAuth 2.0. Agrego, built on ASP.NET MVC, offers a structured platform for agricultural stakeholders, implementing ASP.NET Identity 2.0 for role-based data access and storing production data in an MS SQL database.

To achieve semantic interoperability, the project adopts the Agriculture Information Model (AIM), which aligns with established standards like OWL Time, GeoSPARQL, and SSN. AIM supports structured data exchange and integration with the DATAMITE platform.

Datasets from eDWIN and Agrego, including weather data, pest observations, market data, and production records, are processed and shared within the DATAMITE ecosystem. These datasets follow a structured ingestion process, ensuring compatibility with AIM. Data pipelines have been developed for normalisation and integration, utilising the [FOODIE](#) toolset for structured data processing.

A key component of Pilot 5 is the establishment of the Polish Agricultural Data Space (Pontus-X) for secure data sharing. Hosted on PSNC's OpenShift PaaS Cloud, the deployment includes a portal and a provider component. The system integrates with the Gaia-X framework, enabling compliant and secure data exchanges. The publication of datasets on Pontus-X leverages the Nautilus library (<https://github.com/deltaDAO/nautilus>), facilitating blockchain-based asset transactions and access management through smart contracts.

Overall, Pilot 5 has successfully established an interoperable data-sharing ecosystem, aligning agricultural datasets with AIM standards and ensuring secure transactions through Pontus-X. Future steps include optimising data pipelines and expanding dataset availability to enhance usability for stakeholders.

3.5.2 Demonstrator

Documents and demos are shown here.

Test scenario 1 - Automatic collection of data sets from related systems:

Weather data can be obtained directly from the service, extended to support returning data in the target AIM model for the DATAMITE project; swagger for the API specification can be found under the following link (meteo-controller-aim section of the API):

<https://dev.DATAMITE.psnc.pl/api/meteo/v1/api/swagger-ui/index.html>

For example, to obtain the latest reading from station PME22 in AIM model / JSON-LD format service returns it with the following request:

<https://dev.datamite.psnc.pl/api/meteo/v1/aim/meteo/station/PME22/latest>

Test scenario 2 - Creation and deployment of data pipelines

The data harmonisation pipelines are part of the "Data harmonisation" component of DATAMITE. The pipelines have been used to harmonise and enable access to data from Pilot5, as we will show in the next video.

Pilot 5 data harmonisation video:

<https://box.pionier.net.pl/f/4c03cc87133c489d95a9/?dl=1>

Test scenario 3 - Configuration of infrastructure and deployment of DATAMITE platform and necessary components

DATAMITE Platform has been deployed on Pilot 5 infrastructure, but the access is not open to the public at the time and is accessible only from the internal network. The Deployed platform with initial evaluation is shown on screenshots in Appendix B.

Test scenario 4 - Deployment of data space/marketplace for agri-food domain in Poland

Pontus-X (Polish Agricultural Data Space) has been deployed and is hosted at:

<https://dataspaces.psnc.pl/>

Test scenario 6 - Use the DATAMITE platform to publish data products on the Polish Agricultural Data Space.

This test scenario is still under development. In terms of Pilot 5, we managed to share our data sets as Pontus-X assets directly from Pilot 5 services.

Pilot 5 data sharing video on Pontus-X:

Showcase of publishing assets (data products) on the Pontus-X framework, used as a target data space for Pilot 5. Based on this implementation Pontus-X Plugin Broker for DATAMITE will be implemented and integrated into the DATAMITE platform.

<https://box.pionier.net.pl/f/9185e55505c3418bbcdc/?dl=1>

3.6 Pilot 6: Connecting MISTRAL to the EU AIoD Platform Demonstrator

3.6.1 Current status

Currently, the implementation of Pilot 6 focuses on integrating the Meteo Italian supercomputing portal (MISTRAL: <https://www.mistralportal.it/it/>) with the European AI on Demand (AIoD) data space as part of the DATAMITE project. The process of developing mechanisms for distributing meteorological data through European portals is underway, aiming to increase data accessibility and open new business and collaboration opportunities. Simultaneously, data quality control tools are being implemented to ensure consistency and accuracy for various applications, such as weather forecasting for agriculture, energy, and crisis management. In the next stages, training materials will be prepared on meteorological data storage formats and their use across different economic sectors.

3.6.2 Demonstrator

Pilot 6 aims to use DATAMITE for two main objectives, which are explained in the Test Scenarios section of report D5.1. Currently, testing of the MISTRAL data dissemination is underway, and below is an explanation of the roadmap for data preparation and connection to the ad hoc AIoD broker, which is currently in pre-production. The videos of the demos can be found at <https://gitlab.hpc.cineca.it/bchandr1/datamite>

Dataset creation

At the outset, the first stage of dissemination relates to the preparation of the relevant dataset and the corresponding data product. For this we use a local instance of the DATAMITE instance. The creation of the dataset is shown in “Demo1 on the GitLab repository” provided above. After the dataset has been created, the data file, in our case a json catalogue, contains various relevant information about data availability, license, ownership etc., for each individual dataset, is uploaded (or directly fetched from a URL) through the front-end DATAMITE service.

Data product creation

The next step after creating a dataset is to create a data product, which is simply a more refined output that turns data (often datasets) into a usable tool, application or service by adding an additional layer of specifications, such as user-defined policies. The "Demo2 on the GitLab repository" highlights the usefulness of the data product composition module. The demo currently

uses an off-site installation. Once the data product has been prepared here, it is ready to be distributed using the AIoD broker discussed below.

AIoD broker for dissemination

The ad-hoc Broker module functionality has been described in detail in D2.3. In short, the module enables seamless publication of metadata to the AI on Demand (AIoD) platform that works via a REST API but also takes into account other publishing technologies.

AIoD broker repository:

<https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/DATAMITE-project/data-sharing/brokers-eu-portals>

At present, the brokering service prototype works as intended but is isolated from the rest of the system. The team is currently working on integrating data brokers with the data product composition tool in order to automate the publication process. Once data products are defined from the MISTRAL data catalogue, we will be able to produce a complete demo of the whole workflow.

4 Conclusions

At this stage of the DATAMITE project, implemented through pilot demonstrators, system components have been integrated, and the first stage of tests has been conducted to confirm the correctness of the adopted architecture and the functionality of the modules. The presented demos and videos show how DATAMITE solutions improve data exchange in various environments. In general, we focused on data collection, transformation and validation. For this purpose, metadata unification and, above all, setting up environments were also performed.

A crucial element was the advanced CI/CD infrastructure. Using tools such as GitLab Repository and DockerHub enabled the implementation of automated pipelines that regularly perform testing, compiling, and deploying new software versions. In the current phase of the project, release number 1 of the DATAMITE framework has been implemented.

Further work will focus on finalising the integration of all components, extending the data flow automation, implementing the quality assessment module and further releases and integrations of components in the next demonstrator version scheduled for M32 (D5.4).

At this early stage of evaluation, the integration of key components of the DATAMITE framework is progressing, although some components remain in the early testing phases. This can be seen at different levels of pilot advancement. Current testing suggests the viability of the adopted architecture, and pilots can implement the components as they are developed. As progress is made, key performance indicators (KPIs) are planned to be evaluated to provide concrete, quantitative evidence of the benefits of adopting the DATAMITE framework. These metrics will allow us to objectively assess performance, scalability, and overall impact across a range of environments. Future iterations of the demonstrators will incorporate these metrics to provide a more detailed and technical assessment of the system's effectiveness and potential areas for improvement.

Appendix A: Pilot 2 test scenarios queries

Query I

```

WITH unified_data AS (
    SELECT
        s.ssnnumber,
        s.customerstatuscode,
        s.customersincedate,
        s.productkey,
        s.markettype,
        g.telecomservice,
        g.offerdiscounts,
        g.totalbill,
        g.producttypekey,
        g.benefits,
        p.maincabin,
        p.switchserialnumber,
        p.networkprovider,
        p.orderflag,
        p.services,
        p.systemerp
        FROM mariadb.siebel.customer_data s
        JOIN mariadb.geneva.telecom_services g
        ON s.ssnnumber = g.ssnnumber
        JOIN mongodb.promitheas.network_data p
        ON s.productkey = p.switchserialnumber
        WHERE s.customerstatuscode = 'Active'

    UNION ALL

    SELECT
        s.ssnnumber,
        s.customerstatuscode,
        s.customersincedate,
        s.productkey,
        s.markettype,
        g.telecomservice,
        g.offerdiscounts,
        g.totalbill,
        g.producttypekey,
        g.benefits,
        p.maincabin,
        p.switchserialnumber,
        p.networkprovider,
        p.orderflag,
        p.services,
        p.systemerp
        FROM mariadb.siebel.customer_data s
        JOIN mongodb.promitheas.network_data p
        ON s.productkey = p.switchserialnumber
        JOIN mariadb.geneva.telecom_services g
        ON s.ssnnumber = g.ssnnumber
        WHERE s.customerstatuscode = 'Active'

```



```

        AND p.orderflag = 'Open'
    )
SELECT
    networkprovider,
    COUNT(*) AS total_entries,
    SUM(CASE WHEN totalbill IS NULL OR totalbill = '' THEN 1 ELSE 0 END) AS
missing_totalbill_count,
    SUM(CASE WHEN orderflag IS NULL OR orderflag = '' THEN 1 ELSE 0 END) AS
missing_orderflag_count
FROM unified_data
WHERE maincabin LIKE '43%'
GROUP BY networkprovider
ORDER BY total_entries DESC;

```

Query II

```

BEGIN TRANSACTION;

-- Step 1: Identify High-Paying Customers at Risk of Leaving
WITH high_value_customers AS (
    SELECT s.ssnnumber,
           s.customerstatuscode,
           s.customersincedate,
           g.totalbill,
           g.startedcontract,
           g.producttypekey,
           g.benefits,
           COUNT(o.otherproducts) AS additional_products
    FROM mariadb.siebel.customer_data s
    JOIN mariadb.geneva.telecom_services g
    ON s.ssnnumber = g.ssnnumber
    LEFT JOIN mariadb.siebel.customer_data o
    ON s.ssnnumber = o.ssnnumber
    WHERE g.totalbill > 50 -- Consider high-paying customers (e.g., over 50 EUR
per month)
    AND (g.startedcontract BETWEEN DATE_SUB(CURRENT_DATE, INTERVAL 2 MONTH) AND
CURRENT_DATE
    OR g.startedcontract <= DATE_ADD(CURRENT_DATE, INTERVAL 15 DAY)) --
Contracts ending soon
    GROUP BY s.ssnnumber, s.customerstatuscode, s.customersincedate, g.totalbill,
g.startedcontract, g.producttypekey, g.benefits
)

-- Step 2: Flag These Customers for Contract Renewal Engagement
UPDATE mariadb.customer_engagement ce
SET engagement_status = 'Pending Renewal Offer'
WHERE ce.ssnnumber IN (SELECT ssnnumber FROM high_value_customers);

-- Step 3: Insert New Customers from Geneva into Siebel if They Don't Already
Exist
INSERT INTO mariadb.siebel.customer_data (ssnnumber, customerstatuscode,
customersincedate, productkey, markettype)
SELECT g.ssnnumber,

```

```

        'New',
CURRENT_DATE,
g.producttypekey,
        'B2C'
FROM mariadb.geneva.telecom_services g
WHERE g.ssnnumber NOT IN (SELECT ssnnumber FROM
mariadb.siebel.customer_data);

-- Step 4: Update Order Status in Promitheas for Pending Orders
UPDATE mongodb.promitheas.network_data p
SET orderflag = 'Fulfilled'
WHERE orderflag = 'Pending'
AND EXISTS (
        SELECT 1 FROM mariadb.siebel.customer_data s
        WHERE s.productkey = p.switchserialnumber
        AND s.customerstatuscode = 'Active'
);

-- Step 5: Insert Audit Log for Updated Orders
INSERT INTO mariadb.audit_logs (transaction_id, change_type, affected_table,
timestamp)
SELECT
UUID(),
        'UPDATE',
        'network_data',
CURRENT_TIMESTAMP
FROM mongodb.promitheas.network_data
WHERE orderflag = 'Fulfilled';

-- Step 6: Delete Old Records from Geneva Older Than 5 Years
DELETE FROM mariadb.geneva.telecom_services
WHERE startedcontract < DATE_SUB(CURRENT_DATE, INTERVAL 5 YEAR);

-- Step 7: Generate a Network Summary Report
INSERT INTO mariadb.reports.network_summary
SELECT s.ssnnumber,
s.customerstatuscode,
s.customersincedate,
g.telecomservice,
g.totalbill,
p.networkprovider,
p.orderflag,
h.additional_products -- Extra services such as Payzy, TV, Mobile, Insurance
FROM mariadb.siebel.customer_data s
JOIN mariadb.geneva.telecom_services g ON s.ssnnumber = g.ssnnumber
JOIN mongodb.promitheas.network_data p ON s.productkey = p.switchserialnumber
LEFT JOIN high_value_customers h ON s.ssnnumber = h.ssnnumber
WHERE p.maincabin LIKE '43%';

-- Commit the transaction if all operations succeed
COMMIT;

-- If any error occurs, rollback everything
EXCEPTION WHEN ERROR THEN
ROLLBACK;

```

Appendix B: Pilot 5 DATAMITE platform deployment

Main view of the DATAMITE deployment for Pilot 5

Definition of wind speed term for Agriculture domain.

• Bulk ◦ Streaming ◦ Database Connection ×

File name
PME22.csv

File type
csv

Field Delimiter Decimal Delimiter

Import the file

↻ PME22.csv

Create

Uploading dataset in csv format with meteorological data.

Pending approval by the E...